

THE MORAL AND EDUCATIONAL FUNCTION OF GAMES IN THE PRIMARY SCHOOL

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Annotation: Games are among the traditional and mass phenomena of multitasking, ethno-pedagogical nature, which occupy a special place in children's activities. They are an inseparable part of the national culture. In all nations, games are considered an invaluable cultural asset of that nation. Because the way of life, traditions, spiritual world, outlook, moral and aesthetic views of each people are reflected in them.

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The image of the nation, its past, present and future are shown in the games. It is difficult to imagine the life of children without games. Each of the games is an independent work of folklore. Its first examples were created in ancient times, and for centuries it served the role of self-education, adaptation to existing conditions, and training for the younger generation. The physical-educational and spiritual-ethical views tested in the life experience of the people and brought to the spirit of the nation are reflected in the games. They encourage children to be honest, truthful and honest, brave, humane and kind. After all, most games are in the form of a competition, and one of the conditions for a positive conclusion is honesty.

Games have a social, physiological and aesthetic significance in the life of children. The social significance of games is that the child lives and plays directly in the bosom of nature and society, in the bosom of the family. The child gets close to nature through the game. The student takes the necessary objects for his game: branches, leaves, clay, stones, etc. from nature. Most of the games are arranged in quiet corners of nature: by the water, at the edge of the stream, at the foot of the

mountains, at the edge of the caves, in the shade of the trees. Or many children feed and care for an animal as a game, or grow a plant. The child will enjoy all this.

Children follow the lifestyle and work of adults and assimilate the life of society. Children do not remain indifferent to the various realities that take place in the family environment: hospitality, doing household chores, fighting for a living. Children directly observe and copy them, and they imitate them in their play activities. In this way, children's readiness for life and participation in society is ensured.

The physiological importance of games is that through it the child can satisfy his natural-biological, spiritual-physical needs. Because physical activity is one of the main factors important for the healthy and proper growth of a child, it has been specially noted by medical staff. Games help children to grow up healthy, strong, fit and agile. Through games, children's body parts develop (normally) and become strong.

The aesthetic value of games is that the child derives spiritual pleasure and satisfaction from them. Games are able to influence a child's emotions to such an extent that as a result, even in the child's heart love, aspiration, various positive qualities and lofty dreams can be born. For example, the dream of becoming a pilot in the heart of a child flying a kite or playing with a toy airplane, and the desire of a child drawing crooked pictures on the asphalt to become an artist in the future, are born only at a certain moment of the game. At the same time, children's interest and attention to these games become serious, fall into a certain path, and finally grow to the level of choosing a profession.

So, it is possible to witness that every situation observed in life is absorbed into children's games. This shows that the games are extremely connected with social life, nature, society, and life.

It is important that games play an important role in children's healthy, beauty-conscious lives. Although the main goal of games is actually for children to master life, to acquire various skills and abilities, to try to look at life with the eyes of love,

to spend time effectively, which is the few moments given as life, there are also specific goals that come from the same general goal.

The special purpose of the games is reflected in its multitasking. For example, while children play action games related to the name of animals, although they consider enjoyment through it as the main goal, loving an animal, taking care of it, and learning about the specific aspects of that animal's movement are seen as a private goal.

As you can see, games, like other genres of folklore, are multifunctional. Its main tasks are as follows:

The moral and educational function of games. This task specific to the games comes from the life lesson-moral training in their essence. Therefore, in most games, it is observed that a number of human and positive qualities are praised, such as the idea of being hardworking, the idea of encouraging the acquisition of professional secrets, or rescuing a friend who is "in a difficult situation", honoring friendship, ensuring the game ends with victory by showing bravery, and protecting the team's honor. Therefore, games educate children in the best human qualities such as hard work, friendship, honesty, correctness, honesty, loyalty, patriotism, bravery, bravery, learning, knowledge, resourcefulness, intelligence, dexterity. He urges children towards spiritual beauty, virtue and goodness, and calls them to fight for the good of the country.

People's views on spiritual qualities are reflected in games in a unique form and artistic style. Therefore, games have a special place in the system of our moral values and are passed down from generation to generation over centuries.

The idea of calling for the protection of the motherland, urging to preserve the interests of the country, the people, encouraging one's own interests to serve the interests of the motherland, and showing the value of love and loyalty to the motherland is figuratively embedded in the composition of traditional folk games. These ideas are vividly understood in the example of the games "Fortress defense"

or “Fortress defense”, “White poplar, blue poplar”, “White rice, blue rice”, “Get the flag”, “Travel to cities”.

In the game “Fortress defense”, children are divided into two opposing sides and appoint a chief (captain) for themselves. The game is played on a large field or in a hall. Three large, medium and small circles are drawn in the center of the field (hall). A small circle is considered a kurgan (fortress), and in its center, a shape is made of sand. One side defends the bastion and waits for the attackers above the middle circle line. Attackers must attack the rampart from the large circle line, trick the defenders and jump over the formation on the rampart.

The defenders of the fortress block the way of the attackers, touch them and try to capture them. The defender, who misses the attacker without touching his hands, becomes a prisoner and leaves the game. The defenders of the fortress can capture only the attacker who passes from the right side. The attacker can only be touched, it is not possible to hold. Only one attacker passes in front of one guard. Majority does not count. In the game, a boy acts as a judge, counts and controls those who jumped from the fortress and those who were captured. Only one attacker passes in front of one guard. Majority does not count. In the game, a boy acts as a judge, counts and controls those who jumped from the fortress and those who were captured. Both a jump and a capture are worth one point each. The side with the most points wins. The children of the winning side lined up and shouted three times “Hurrah, hurrah!” they shout.

In this game, a lively image of patriots and patriots is created, who go to the battlefield to fight against those who want to take possession of someone else’s land or property, and strive to save their land and property.

Every detail and episode of the game embodies the image of young patriots who are fighting hard to protect their motherland, the motherland, to save it from the attacks of the enemies. Because in this game, children feel that they are not just protecting a toy-toy made of sand in a simple circle, but that they are protecting their

whole motherland, country, people who live in it - their fellow citizens. It is this feeling that grows in their hearts to the level of true patriotism.

The game “Defence of the Fortress” not only educates the children’s sense of patriotism, but also encourages them to fight. Through this game, children acquire skills of dexterity, left-handedness, and intelligence. They will be informed about some of the training related to the basic military training. Looking at the use of the words “prisoner”, “defender” and “attacker” in the game “Defence of the Fortress”, which was created for the purpose of teaching children to basic military education, it is possible to understand that this game was created with the intention of teaching children to defend the homeland and the people, thereby increasing their military fighting ability.

It is well known that taking a prisoner in battle is frowned upon among warriors. Because the enemy’s desire to put the prisoner in various physical challenges and learn from him the weak points of his opponent’s defense has been tested many times in real life experiences. In many cases, the captives could not bear the physical torture and gave up their secrets. That’s why many preferred to die a valiant death in battle rather than being captured. This was also observed in the example of Tomaris’s son Sparganis, who was captured by deception. This life event is interpreted in a unique way in children’s war novel-type games created by means of imagination. Therefore, in children’s games, the idea of trying not to be “captured” by the opponent’s side, and hurrying to save fellow comrades who have been “captured” as much as possible, is leading. Because each “captive” player accelerates and facilitates the defeat of his side. Therefore, children try to be as agile and alert as possible, not to be “captured”.

The ending of the game with the winning side shouting “Hurrah!” three times shows that it has a combat-military essence and is formed on the basis of life experiences, skills and views of focusing on the defense of the homeland. In fact, the forces that destroyed the enemy in the battles and ended the battle with victory announced that it was over with the sounds of “Hurrah!”.

In conclusion, games require the child to use his physical strength and mind appropriately and correctly. Affecting the children's psyche and spirituality, it activates and develops their mind, and thinking ability.

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